

FerryBox-assisted monitoring of mixed layer pH in the Norwegian Coastal Current

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Highlights:

- Automated, flow-through, spectrophotometric pH detector was developed for FerryBox platforms
- *In situ* uncertainty <0.003 and compliant with best practices
- Norwegian Coastal Current wintertime pH was relatively low and stable
- Spring and summertime pH was higher and more variable, coincident with higher chlorophyll

Abstract

The evaluation of marine carbonate system variability and the impacts of ocean acidification (OA) on coastal marine ecosystems increasingly rely on monitoring platforms capable of delivering near real-time *in situ* carbonate system observations. These observations are also used for developing models and scenarios of OA, including potential impacts on marine ecosystem structure and function. An embedded flow-through spectrophotometric pH detection system has been developed alongside an underway seawater sampling system - termed a FerryBox - operating on ships of opportunity (SOOP), and can deliver a continuous data stream of mixed layer seawater pH with an *in situ* uncertainty of <0.003. We report metrological approaches behind the pH detection procedure and the evaluation of dye addition perturbation with analytical precision as low as 0.0005. In addition, we present field-based observations from a deployment of the pH detection system along the Norwegian Coastal Current in winter, spring, and summer periods of 2015. Spring and summertime pH was generally ~0.1 higher, and up to ~0.255 higher, in comparison to winter pH observations. Here we show the necessity for a regular, high density monitoring approach, and the suitability of this pH detection technique for unmanned observational platforms.

1 I. INTRODUCTION

2 The oceans have been recognized as an important sink of CO₂ emissions from anthropogenic sources
3 (e.g., Doney et al., 2009; Sabine et al., 2004). This is in large part due to time series observations and models for
4 estimating ocean-atmosphere interactions. Dissolved CO₂ in the ocean's surface produces carbonic acid that
5 dissociates releasing hydrogen ions. The net result of CO₂ uptake is an increase in hydrogen ion concentration -
6 hence a decrease in pH - commonly referred to as ocean acidification (OA) (Doney et al., 2009).

7 The need for understanding the changing chemistry of the ocean and the impacts of OA on marine
8 ecosystems has catalysed the development of platforms and technologies capable of observing the marine
9 carbonate system at suitable space-time resolution. Coastal regions, in particular, present a challenging
10 environment for carbonate system observations due to processes including, but not limited to, freshwater input,
11 mixing and transport, interaction with shelf geochemistry, and large seasonal algal blooms. Gathering the
12 required field data using conventional sampling efforts (i.e., research cruises) is demanding in terms of costs and
13 logistics, and, due to relatively poor spatial and temporal coverage, do not have the required resolution for
14 observing high frequency or regionally-specific variability (Hofmann et al., 2011; McNeil and Sasse, 2016).
15 Recent efforts have shown great promise in reducing these costs by taking advantage of ships of opportunity
16 (SOOP), container or passenger ships that regularly operate along transects, as mobile platforms for oceanic data
17 collection using pump and sensor packages called FerryBoxes (Petersen, 2014). These systems can collect
18 oceanographic and atmospheric data from physical, biogeochemical, and meteorological sensors coupled with
19 GPS information, and in some cases provide satellite-based ship to shore data transfer.

20 The commercial availability of instruments for measuring the seawater carbonate system variables -
21 partial pressure of carbon dioxide (pCO₂), pH, total alkalinity (AT), and total dissolved inorganic carbon (CT) -
22 is a testament of the maturity of technology for underway and autonomous OA observations (Martz et al., 2015).
23 In the case of AT and CT, reliable and high quality measurements still rely on benchtop set-ups for fulfilling
24 "climate" level analytical figures of merit (Newton et al. 2014). In terms of autonomous carbonate system
25 observations, a promising approach comes from simultaneous spectrophotometric detection of CT and pH, in
26 which a three-week time-series deployment of an autonomous system achieved ~4 μmol kg⁻¹ and 0.0025
27 accuracy, respectively (Wang et al., 2015).

28 The development of systems for unattended spectrophotometric measurement of pH using an indicator
29 dye, both for ship-based continuous underway measurements and autonomous *in situ* devices, has indeed re-
30 ceived renewed interest during last two decades for improved schemes based on the cost effectiveness of
31 miniaturized spectrophotometers, mini-fluidic techniques, and embedded systems (for underway: Aßmann et al.,
32 2011; Bellerby et al., 2002; DelValls, 1999; Mosley et al., 2004; Ohline et al., 2007; Reggiani et al., 2014;
33 Rérolle et al., 2013; Tapp et al., 2000; Wang et al., 2007; Yang et al., 2014; and for *in situ*: Kaltenbacher et al.,
34 2000; Liu et al., 2006; Martz et al., 2003; Nakano et al., 2006; Seidel et al., 2008). Spectrophotometric
35 techniques have the unique advantage that no calibration is required for evaluation of pH on total scale, as long
36 as the behaviour of a specific indicator in seawater has been characterized in terms of absorbance and
37 protonation and then reported to measurement conditions. Major differences between the above-mentioned
38 spectrophotometric pH systems include the pathlength through which light absorption is measured, the light
39 source (tungsten, light emitting diode, etc.), modes of mixing sample and reagents (mixing coil, stir bar, etc.),

1 temperature at which measurements are made (controlled or *in situ*), and sample analysis time (including
2 performing blank and dye perturbation measurements).

3 In this article, we discuss the development of a flow-through, spectrophotometric, underway pH
4 detection instrument coupled to a FerryBox system that has been previously described in Reggiani et al. (2014).
5 The system has been custom-designed to address several factors: resistance to biofouling, a sampling rate high
6 enough to follow the highly dynamic coastal environment, analytical resolution better than 0.001, long-term
7 stability, ease of installation and operation by untrained personnel, low power and low cost, open-source
8 architecture for future development, and integration with unmanned surface vehicles. The principle of operation
9 will be described with emphasis on methods which were used to provide the accuracy and precision required to
10 meet the “weather” and the “climate” achievements: the former indicates the capability to identify relative spatial
11 patterns and short-term variations underlying impacts on local, immediate dynamics of ocean acidification, the
12 latter high confidence level measurements capable of assessing long-term trends (multi-decadal time scales) in
13 order to detect anthropogenic driven changes on carbon chemistry (Newton et al., 2014). Observational data
14 including temperature, salinity, chlorophyll a fluorescence, and pH from five cruises along the Norwegian coast
15 between winter and summer of 2015 will also be presented.

17 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

18 **2.1. The spectrophotometric pH detection system**

19 The pH detection scheme is based on the embedded-spectrophotometry flow-through system described
20 in Bellerby et al. (2002) and modified as described in Reggiani et al. (2014) (Fig. 1). A detailed description of
21 the standalone detection system is presented in Reggiani et al. (2014). Briefly, the pH sensor relies on water flow
22 generated by the main FerryBox peristaltic pump that delivers a continuous flow of seawater from an inlet pipe
23 that is situated at ~3-5 meters depth and provides seawater directly from the other side of the ship’s hull. The
24 flow-through set-up hosts a custom-designed PTFE flow cell with a nominal pathlength of 38 mm and a sample
25 volume of 8 ml. The flow cell is fitted with a custom designed magnetic mixing bar and a miniature glass
26 encapsulated thermistor (Honeywell; calibrated to 0.01°C) that is signal-conditioned and interfaced to the control
27 unit. The light source is provided by four light emitting diodes (LEDs; 435 nm, 494 nm, 596 nm, and 750 nm;
28 Roithner) and light is detected with a spectrophotometer that covers the region between 350 nm and 800 nm with
29 a wavelength resolution of 1.5 nm, a 25 µm slit width, and 14 bits A/D signal conversion (OceanOptics STS
30 VIS-NIR).

32 **2.2. Principle of the spectrophotometric method**

33 Hydrogen ion concentration on the total scale (Zeebe and Wolf-Gladrow, 2001) in seawater has been
34 demonstrated to be related to the second dissociation constant (K_2) of an indicator dye (I), the ratio (R) between
35 two absorbance levels produced by the indicator in seawater at the wavelengths corresponding to absorbance
36 maxima of unprotonated (I^{2-}) and monoprotonated (HI^-) forms, and a set of molar absorption ratios (e_i) as a
37 function of temperature (Clayton and Byrne, 1993):

$$39 \text{pH}_T = \text{p}K_2 + \log\left(\frac{R-e_1}{e_2-R\cdot e_3}\right) \quad (1a)$$

1 where $\text{pH}_T = -\log[\text{H}^+]_T$, $[\text{H}^+]_T = [\text{H}^+] + [\text{HSO}_4^-]$ and $K_2 = [\text{H}^+]_T[\text{I}^{2-}][\text{HI}^-]^{-1}$ (1b)

2
3 Suitable indicators, for example *m*-cresol purple and thymol blue, have been characterized in terms of
4 absorbance and proton exchange behaviour (Clayton and Byrne, 1993; Zhang and Byrne, 1996) and extensively
5 used for seawater pH measurements. Such characterizations provide stoichiometric models for the HI^- and I^{2-}
6 forms for a range of salinity and temperatures. The following relationship has been empirically derived for
7 thymol blue for $5\text{ }^\circ\text{C} \leq \text{temperature (T)} \leq 35\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $30 \leq \text{salinity (S)} \leq 40$ (Zhang and Byrne, 1996):

8
9
$$\text{p}K_2 = 4.706 S/T + 26.3300 - 7.17218 \log T - 0.017316 S$$
 (2)

10
11 where T in equation (2) is in $^\circ\text{K}$. As long as T and S for the sample are measured and a complete set of spectral
12 data relative to the measurement are recorded, the model of the indicator can be refined through post-processing
13 to improve accuracy of the calculated pH. DelValls and Dickson (1998) reported the investigation of pH through
14 high quality electrode-based measurements of buffers based on 2-amino-2-hydroxymethyl-1,3-propanediol (Tris)
15 in synthetic sea water; based on their recommendation, the $\text{p}K_2$ value of our non-purified thymol blue dye has
16 been adjusted by adding 0.0047 to pH obtained at measurement conditions.

17 18 **2.3. Operation**

19 Prior to a programmed sampling sequence, a set of ancillary data is retrieved from the FerryBox:
20 temperature of the water at the ship's inlet, salinity, time, and coordinates. The light source is switched off and a
21 dark spectrum is acquired with the programmed integration time. Transmission levels may vary during a long
22 term deployment; hence the system adjusts spectral counts at the detector, acting on each of the LED currents,
23 the spectrophotometer integration time, and the number of spectra for averaging (the latter defining the total
24 integration time). In this way the LEDs are kept to the lowest current compatible with a minimum spectrometer
25 integration time, thus preventing degradation of the LEDs, keeping the spectrophotometer far from saturation
26 and, at the same time, with a suitable signal/noise rejection related to the total integration time.

27 The water sample to be analysed is introduced into the system, then the water flow is stopped and the
28 system checks that the light levels corresponding to analysis wavelengths are stable; a set of blank (seawater)
29 spectra is acquired and logged, as well as the actual temperature of the sample. A dye solution of 2 mM thymol
30 blue sodium salt (Aldrich) in deionized water ($\rho > 1\text{ M}\Omega\text{ cm}$) is pumped into the sample at a mixing ratio of
31 around 0.005 with absorbance at 435 nm around 0.8. The concentration of the dye in the sample + dye solution is
32 proportional to the absorbance (A_{iso}) at the isosbestic wavelength of thymol blue (494 nm). The constant of this
33 linear relationship is determined empirically and is proper for the optical pathlength. The change in salinity of
34 the sample can be estimated using the mixing ratio.

35 After measuring the absorbance of the sample, a sequence of up to four indicator dye addition steps is
36 performed to evaluate the dye perturbation effect on sample pH. These dye perturbation steps measure
37 absorbance levels at higher indicator concentrations and, in general, at different temperatures. All spectral
38 acquisitions are performed when light levels sensed by the spectrophotometer's charge-coupled device (CCD)
39 are stable (mixing and settling time). Temperature drift of the sample is strictly connected to flow cell
40 temperature and thermal isolation. Under normal underway operations, where the cuvette is being continuously

1 flushed, a maximum drift of 0.02 °C is observed during post injection collection of a single averaged spectrum.
 2 Temperature stability of the flow cell is helped by the flushing and pre-equilibration with *in situ* seawater during
 3 flushing step of the sampling sequence operation, and this has proven to be crucial for achieving high precision
 4 and preventing changes in the light beam geometry due to thermal expansion (around 100 ppm/°C for PTFE). It
 5 is worth of remarking that temperature homogeneity of the sample is also very important. Measurements with
 6 thermistors on the four sides of the flow cell confirmed that the temperature drift is limited to 0.02 °C and that
 7 such drift occurs in a uniform way along the light path.

8 9 **2.4. Evaluation of absorbance levels**

10 Absorbance measured at a specific wavelength (A_λ) of the detection system is defined as:

$$11 \quad A_\lambda = \log \frac{I_i(\lambda)}{I_o(\lambda)} \quad (3)$$

12 given light intensities at the input (I_i) and output (I_o) of the flow cell. Strictly, the input intensity refers to the
 13 collimated beam emerging from the input window (glass/sample discontinuity) and the output intensity refers to
 14 the beam arriving to the output window (sample/glass discontinuity).

15 Using absorbance measured at three wavelengths for seawater: $^{bk}A_{435}$, $^{bk}A_{596}$, $^{bk}A_{ir}$, and seawater +
 16 dye $^{pi}A_{435}$, $^{pi}A_{596}$, $^{pi}A_{ir}$, the rigorous method for calculating the absorbance ratio R comes from the following
 17 equations, where superscripts bk , pi and, ir represent blank, post-injection, and infrared reference, respectively:

$$18 \quad R = \frac{A_{596}}{A_{435}} = \frac{^{pi}A_{596} - ^{bk}A_{596} - (^{pi}A_{ir} - ^{bk}A_{ir})}{^{pi}A_{435} - ^{bk}A_{435} - (^{pi}A_{ir} - ^{bk}A_{ir})} \quad (4)$$

19 If we replace the absorbance with the logarithm:

$$20 \quad A_{596} = \log \frac{^{pi}I_{i,596}}{^{pi}I_{o,596}} - \log \frac{^{bk}I_{i,596}}{^{bk}I_{o,596}} - \log \frac{^{pi}I_{i,ir}}{^{pi}I_{o,ir}} + \log \frac{^{bk}I_{i,ir}}{^{bk}I_{o,ir}} \quad (5)$$

21 and we consider that the input light intensities are stable, i.e., $^{pi}I_{i,\lambda} = ^{bk}I_{i,\lambda}$, then equation (5) can be written as:

$$22 \quad A_{596} = \log \frac{^{bk}I_{o,596}}{^{pi}I_{o,596}} - \log \frac{^{bk}I_{o,ir}}{^{pi}I_{o,ir}} \quad (6a)$$

23 and likewise:

$$24 \quad A_{435} = \log \frac{^{bk}I_{o,435}}{^{pi}I_{o,435}} - \log \frac{^{bk}I_{o,ir}}{^{pi}I_{o,ir}} \quad (6b)$$

25 Such equations can be taken into the measurement process as good estimates of absorbance when the
 26 dominant contribution of fluctuations in the input light intensities are the short term ones; these can be
 27 effectively rejected limiting the observation with a proper integration time. Intensities that have been reported so
 28 far are those obtained by subtracting the dark spectrum (no input light) from actual spectral counts read by the
 29 spectrophotometer during the measurement process, and then corrected for non-linearity of the detector.

30 31 **2.5. Infrared correction and dye addition effects**

32 The infrared absorbance (A_{ir}) is used to remove the contribution of shifts of spectral counts from the
 33 absorbance used to calculate the ratio R that are not due to actual indicator absorbance. That is, it should
 34 compensate light intensity variation due to misalignment or losses in the optical path, mainly due to handling and
 35 repositioning of the cuvette after dye addition when using a benchtop spectrophotometer. In this automated
 36 system, the flow cell is the cuvette and it is stationary, so variability caused by repositioning is clearly avoided.
 37 Nevertheless, due to imperfect beam collimation and alignment, changes in the refractive index of the medium

1 can affect beam geometry, and these effects are generally non-uniform across the spectrum (dispersion). The
2 infrared correction is based on the assumption that both HI^- and I^{2-} absorbance are affected in similar ways by
3 such a shift so that we can refer to it as a common mode noise signal. Here, the light source entering the flow cell
4 is produced through the combination of independent sources; hence, short term shifts of light levels entering the
5 flow cell are not correlated. In any case, the absorbance at the infrared reference wavelength, far from the peaks,
6 should be only correlated to losses in the sample and has been observed to have an average value around 0.0008.
7 With R values above 0.4 this shift would be further inherently rejected from evaluation of pH (based on a
8 ratiometric principle) and accounts to the order of the precision.

9 Perturbation of sample pH due to dye addition depends on the difference between sample pH and the
10 dye solution, and on the buffering capacity of the sample. In order to correct for pH perturbation due to dye
11 injection, a series of discrete indicator additions is performed for every sample, where pH is calculated using the
12 $\text{p}K_2$ model and molar absorption ratios at different dye concentrations. This approach assumes that the indicator
13 effects are additive, which is reasonable if the additions are small. Final indicator concentration in the flow cell
14 after perturbation experiments is around $25 \mu\text{M}$. Using the $\text{pH}_T(R,S,T)$ model (Byrne et al., 1988), the zero
15 addition pH value is inferred estimating the intercept of the linear fitting of the set of measured pH values as
16 function of A_{ir} .

17 In order to isolate the dye addition effect *in situ*, the system first reports all pH evaluations to the same
18 temperature, which is the average of the temperatures recorded during additions. Surface seawater pH is strongly
19 anti-correlated to temperature and a linear temperature dependence can be approximated (e.g., mean: $-0.0155 \pm$
20 0.02 K^{-1} over 10 K for five sets of dissociation constants; Millero, 2007). The zero addition intercept has been
21 estimated with a linear regression for each set of measurements, and the root mean square deviation provides the
22 inherent precision for that pH measurement.

23 24 **2.6. Laboratory-based tests of system performance**

25 A series of laboratory-based development was conducted using Tris seawater buffers and CO_2 certified
26 reference material (CRM) (both acquired from Andrew Dickson, Scripps Institution of Oceanography, La Jolla,
27 California, USA). In order to assess analytical uncertainty of the pH measurements, Tris seawater buffers (batch
28 26) and the same indicator dye batch were measured in succession using the sample analysis steps described in
29 the operations, evaluation, and correction (sections 2.3-2.5). For the Tris seawater buffer evaluation, two
30 identical systems were tested using a total of 28 measurements – in the laboratory in March 2015 ($n=8$) with
31 system A, and in June 2015 ($n=8$) and at a field station in Kings Bay, Svalbard in July 2015 ($n=12$) with system
32 B. The Tris seawater buffer measurements were made at different temperatures but normalized to $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using
33 equilibrium equations implemented by CO2SYS (Pierrot et al., 2006) and certified AT and CT values, and
34 standard deviation of each set of measurements was calculated.

35 As both a test of the dye perturbation assessment and to provide a secondary assessment of uncertainty,
36 CO_2 certified reference materials (batch 143) were measured in succession using the same sample analysis steps.
37 Using measured pH and certified AT and CT values, an overdetermination of the carbonate system was executed
38 to test the consistency of the measured pH. For the overdetermination, dissociation constants for carbonic acid
39 K_1 and K_2 (Lueker et al., 2000) and boric acid K_B (Lee et al., 2010) were used in conjunction with CO2SYS

1 (Pierrot et al., 2006). The replicate measurements of CRMs were also used to calculate standard deviation as a
2 secondary assessment of measurement uncertainty.

3 4 **2.7. Field observations on SOOP MS Trollfjord**

5 The spectrophotometric pH system operated autonomously alongside a standard FerryBox system
6 (Volent et al., 2011) on the passenger ship MS *Trollfjord* which operates along the Norwegian coast over five
7 time periods in 2015: 28 February - 6 March, 20 April - 24 April, 5 May - 11 May, 18 June - 24 June, and 21
8 July - 26 July. Each period was of 5-6 days in duration and roughly covered a transect ~4500 km in length along
9 the western coast of Norway from Bergen, Norway (~60 °N) to Kirkenes, Norway (~71 °N). The FerryBox
10 system was flushed and sensors were inspected and cleaned on a monthly basis.

11 During the sampling periods, the pH system measured seawater pH approximately every five minutes –
12 this included dye pH perturbation experiments on each sample and a timing routine that provided adequate
13 spatial resolution for efficient use of indicator dye. Log files with dye perturbation and temperature-corrected pH
14 were merged with log files containing core FerryBox data that included temperature and salinity (SBE45 and
15 SBE38, Sea-Bird Electronics), and chlorophyll fluorescence (microFlu-chlorophyll, TriOS). Temperature and
16 salinity measurements were periodically checked using secondary calibrated temperature probes and discrete
17 salinity samples for laboratory analysis, respectively. Chlorophyll a concentrations ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$) were estimated using
18 chlorophyll a fluorescence calibration slopes generated with phytoplankton cultures of known chlorophyll a
19 concentration. Chlorophyll fluorescence data was not available during the 28 February – 6 March time period.

20 Quality control of the data was performed using multiple routines that flagged data when the ship was
21 performing docking and other logistics-related manoeuvring (the ship makes 34 stops along the Norwegian coast
22 during each transect), when one or more sensors and their system controls were not functioning properly, and/or
23 when seawater temperature at multiple points in the FerryBox system exhibited large variability ($>2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). The
24 latter is indicative of the FerryBox pump either being switched off or the presence of an obstruction in the
25 system. Data were often flagged at the beginning of each transect due to the ship being stationary at port for an
26 extended period of time ($>12\text{ h}$), and extra flushing of the system was required before normal sensor operation.
27 In order to assess spatial and seasonal variation in the Norwegian Coastal Current, observations presented here
28 are limited to water masses with salinity >29 (Mork, 1981). Due to the range of salinity and temperature for
29 which pK_2 of thymol blue has been determined (Zhang and Byrne, 1996), uncertainties for pH observations at
30 salinity <30 and temperature $<5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ may be slightly greater than the estimated *in situ* uncertainty and will be
31 evaluated in a future study.

32 33 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

34 **3.1. Lab-based assessment using Tris seawater buffers and CO₂ certified reference material**

35 Twenty-eight pH measurements of various bottles of Tris seawater buffers (Dickson laboratory, batch
36 26) were made using two different systems that were built to identical specification (Fig. 2). The dye
37 perturbation experiments revealed that, as expected, the buffering capacity of the Tris buffer was sufficient
38 enough that indicator addition did not perturb pH. Within a measurement temperature range of $0.02\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ the
39 variability observed on pH was typically <0.0005 . The measurements were normalized to $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ using the slope
40 of the linear regression between pH and measurement temperature (Fig. 3), and the resulting standard deviation

1 of measurements made by the two separate systems was ~ 0.0004 . Taking into account the 0.002 uncertainty in
 2 pH that was assigned to the prepared Tris seawater buffer, the combined additive uncertainty was < 0.0024 . This
 3 uncertainty meets the “weather” and “climate” objectives of 0.02 and 0.003 in pH, respectively, as determined
 4 by the Global Ocean Acidification Observing Network (Newton et al., 2014).

5 The pH measurements performed on the CO₂ CRMs (batch 143) are shown in Fig. 4. Here, the effect of
 6 dye addition was evident through the ~ 0.0010 - 0.0015 decrease in pH per step of dye addition. Using the pH
 7 measurement, the certified AT value ($2241.04 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$), and CO₂SYS, the sample pH values at 25 °C can be
 8 calculated and resulting mean and standard deviation of these measurements is 7.9247 ± 0.0006 . This uncertainty
 9 agrees well with the uncertainty of the Tris seawater buffers measurements of 0.0004. The pH measurements on
 10 the CO₂ CRMs were further used to perform an overdetermination analysis of the carbonate system (Table 1).
 11 The uncertainty of the CO₂SYS-calculated AT and CT values are $< 0.3 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$ and are within the uncertainty
 12 reported for state-of-the-art techniques used to make certified values that accompany the CRMs (Dickson et al.,
 13 2007).

14 Despite these laboratory-based tests, the accuracy of the system is largely dominated by uncertainties
 15 associated with dye dissociation constants and dye addition (Bellerby et al., 2002), and therefore by the
 16 uncertainty resulting from the estimate of the linear fitting in Fig. 4. The uncertainty from the coefficient used to
 17 report the pH to the same temperature, $\delta(\partial\text{pH}/\partial T)$, accounts for pH uncertainty as a function of temperature.
 18 During the dye addition sequence, temperature may vary up to ± 0.5 °C and the residual uncertainty is on the
 19 order of precision of 0.0005. The system achieves the estimate of the slope of the $\text{pH}(A_{\text{iso}})$ linear fitting to better
 20 than 0.002. With an average 0.4 isosbestic absorbance, the residual uncertainty on pH is < 0.001 . Combined with
 21 uncertainty of 0.002 on the pK for thymol blue (Zhang and Byrne, 1996), the combined uncertainty is the root
 22 mean square of the three uncertainties which is ~ 0.0029 , which is comparable with estimated uncertainty of
 23 0.0024 acquired from the measurements with the Tris seawater buffer.

24 Combining the measurement uncertainty, the uncertainty of the temperature coefficient of pH, and the
 25 uncertainties for *in situ* and measured temperature (respectively, at the inlet of the FerryBox system and inside
 26 the flow cell), the resulting uncertainty introduced by calculation at *in situ* conditions can be written as:

$$27 \delta(\text{pH})_{\text{is}} = \sqrt{[\delta(\text{pH})_{\text{m}}]^2 + \left[\delta\left(\frac{\partial\text{pH}}{\partial T}\right) \cdot (T_{\text{m}} - T_{\text{is}})\right]^2 + [0.016 \cdot (\delta T_{\text{m}} + \delta T_{\text{is}})]^2}. \quad (7)$$

28
 29 Considering that the difference $T_{\text{m}} - T_{\text{is}}$, during normal operations is limited to 1.5 °C and $\delta T_{\text{m}} \approx \delta T_{\text{is}} \approx 0.02$
 30 °C, from a base uncertainty of 0.0024 it follows that the FerryBox-coupled spectrophotometric pH detection
 31 system can determine *in situ* pH with uncertainty of < 0.003 .
 32
 33

34 **3.2. Field-collected pH measurements between February-July 2015 along the Norwegian coast**

35 Data collected by the FerryBox and pH systems on the M/S *Trollfjord* along the Norwegian Coastal
 36 Current between February and July 2015 exhibited large seasonal and regional variability in temperature,
 37 salinity, chlorophyll a (as estimated from fluorescence), and pH (Fig. 5). The major observed changes from
 38 winter to spring to summer include: (1) a ~ 4 - 9 °C warming with wintertime minimum of 2 °C near Kirkenes and
 39 summertime maxima of ~ 13 °C along many parts of the coast south of 70 °N and especially near Kristiansund
 40 and the Lofoten Islands (62 °N and 68 °N); (2) Salinity in winter was relatively stable (mean = 33.2 ± 0.6) while

1 summertime salinity was lower and more variable (July mean = 32.6 ± 1.6), especially near Måløy, Kristiansund,
2 and Trondheim (62-63.5 °N), and near Sandnessjøen (~66 °N); (3) Chlorophyll a maxima were observed in April
3 above ~68 °N with chlorophyll a concentrations reaching $10 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, while moderate chlorophyll a concentrations
4 up to $\sim 3 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ were present throughout region in spring and summer, especially north of 70 °N; and (4)
5 Generally lower pH and lower variability during winter (Feb/Mar 2015 mean = 8.051 ± 0.014) and higher pH
6 and higher variability (2.2 to 3.6-fold higher) in spring and summer (April 2015 mean = 8.138 ± 0.051 ; May
7 2015 mean = 8.150 ± 0.033 ; June 2015 mean = 8.151 ± 0.035 ; July 2015 mean = 8.148 ± 0.031).

8 Southern Norway tended to be lower in pH during the spring and summer months, especially near the
9 opening of the Trondheimsfjord where pH remained < 8.080 throughout the study period, and between Måløy
10 and Ålesund (~62-62.5 °N) with a number of observations < 8.100 in spring and early summer. Regional maxima
11 in pH were quite variable in terms of location and timing, but some pH values as high as 8.247 were observed
12 near Bodø (67 °N) in April, June, and July, as high as 8.295 in the vicinity of the Lofoten Islands (~68 °N) in
13 April and June, as high as 8.272 near Tromsø (70 °N) in April, May, and June, and as high as 8.246 near
14 Kirkenes (70 °N) in May and June. Despite the general relationship between primary production using CO_2 and
15 therefore increasing pH, there was no significant correlation between high chlorophyll a and high pH
16 observations. Similarly, although there were coinciding observations of low salinity and generally lower pH
17 along southern Norway in the spring and summer periods, there was no region-wide correlation between the two
18 variables. This may have been due to water mass heterogeneity forced by large influences of physical processes
19 on pH such as warming, freshwater input, ocean-atmosphere interactions, and or mixing.

20 To put these observations in perspective, the average ~ 0.1 increase in pH which was observed between
21 February/March and the spring/summer months, assuming a constant AT typical for the Norwegian Coastal
22 Current ($2310 \mu\text{mol kg}^{-1}$) and no change in temperature, would result in ~ 80 ppm lower partial pressure of CO_2
23 (pCO_2) (Pierrot et al., 2006). The largest winter to summer change in pH occurred near the Lofoten Islands with
24 a ~ 0.255 increase in pH. Again, assuming a constant AT and temperature, this increase in pH would result in
25 ~ 170 ppm lower pCO_2 . The magnitude of the observed seasonal variability in the carbonate system is large
26 relative to projected decadal scale change (e.g., mean ocean pH by ~ 2040 is projected to decrease by 0.1 in a
27 business as usual scenario; IPCC, 2013). It is therefore important to take seasonal and regional variability in pH
28 and pCO_2 into account when evaluating the projected decadal and century scale changes in the carbonate system
29 – most notably the rise in CO_2 and decline in pH due to fossil fuel CO_2 emissions.

30 31 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

32 Here we have shown that an autonomous pH measurement system capable of theoretical and
33 operational uncertainties of < 0.003 . This has been tested using Tris seawater buffers and seawater CO_2 CRMs
34 with multiple units built to identical specifications. The system has also been deployed on a SOOP covering
35 > 4000 km along the Norwegian coast for a winter-summer observation period. The data reveals hotspots in the
36 Norwegian Coastal Current where there are minima, maxima, and/or high seasonal variability in environmental
37 drivers like temperature, salinity, and pH. Future work will focus on implementing sensors that can provide a
38 second carbonate chemistry variable (e.g., pCO_2 , AT, CO_3^{2-}) to enable a full characterization of the carbonate
39 system. The embedded flow-through spectrophotometry set-up that has been used for the present pH system has
40 been also considered for direct measurement of CO_3^{2-} ion concentration (Easley et al., 2013) as well as for AT

1 (Spaulding et al., 2014). For seawater pCO₂, several equilibrator-style and spectrophotometric systems are
2 currently commercially available.

3 Spectrophotometry combined with embedded systems has been illustrated in this work as the ideal tool
4 for high resolution surface pH survey of coastal environments when supported by FerryBox equipped SOOP.
5 Analytical uncertainties are comparable to the best laboratory analytical techniques and “climate” quality goals
6 are achievable by an autonomous system over extended periods. The operation and integration with other
7 monitoring systems like a FerryBox flow-through system can improve our capability in measuring carbonate
8 chemistry variability and ecosystem response to OA, with the eventual goal of better understanding carbonate
9 system variability in surface coastal waters, contributing to the refinement of biogeochemical models of
10 continental shelf processes, and investigating variability in biogeochemical processes driven by natural and
11 anthropogenic stressors.

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1 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

2
3 **Figure 1.** Schematic of the pH sampling and detection system. (a) light emitting diode light source, (b) power
4 combiner, (c) input optical fiber, (d) output valve, (e) input valve, (f) bypass valve, (g) dye injection port, (h)
5 temperature probe, (i) output optical fibre, (j) spectrophotometer, (k) interface and control unit.

6
7 **Figure 2.** Measurements of pH (total scale) of Tris seawater buffer (batch 26) at various flow cell temperatures
8 ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) based three measurement periods: March 2015 in the laboratory with system A, slope = $0.0310 \text{ pH } ^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$,
9 $n=8$ (\circ), June 2015 in the laboratory with system B, slope = $0.0308 \text{ pH } ^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$, $n=8$ (∇), and July 2015 at a field
10 station with system B, slope = $0.0308 \text{ pH } ^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$, $n=12$ (\square). Error bars represent 1 standard deviation calculated
11 using each set of measurements.

12
13 **Figure 3.** Differences between measured pH (total scale) of Tris seawater buffer shown in Fig. 2 normalized to
14 25°C ($n=28$) and the assigned pH of the Tris seawater buffer (8.0935). Error bars represent 1 standard deviation
15 calculated using each set of measurements. Dashed lines at ± 0.002 represent the assigned uncertainty of the Tris
16 seawater buffer.

17
18 **Figure 4.** Two sample runs showing the relationship between isosbestic absorption (A_{iso}) and pH of CO_2 certified
19 seawater reference material after four indicator dye perturbations. pH (total scale) is reported at the average flow
20 cell temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) during the analysis cycle. The dye perturbation-corrected pH of Batch 143 #1 (B143) is
21 7.9421 at 23.84°C (\circ), and of B143 #2 is 7.9310 at 24.55°C (∇). Error bars represent 1 standard deviation of
22 calculated using each set of measurements.

23
24 **Figure 5.** Transect data of Norwegian Coastal Current mixed layer waters including temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$), salinity,
25 chlorophyll a estimated from fluorescence ($\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$; note that data are plotted on a log scale), and pH (total scale)
26 for the time periods of: a) 28 February - 6 March 2015, b) 20 April - 24 April 2015, c) 5 May - 11 May 2015, d)
27 18 June - 24 June 2015, and e) 21 July - 26 July 2015. Color bars for each variable are shown on the same scale
28 regardless of month for visual clarity. Major landmarks are denoted on the top figure of panel a) as Kirkenes
29 (Ki), Tromsø (T), Lofoten Islands (L), Bodø (Bo), Sandnessjøen (S), Trondheim (T), Kristiansund (Kr), and
30 Bergen (Be). Chlorophyll a fluorescence data were not available for the 28 February - 6 March 2015 period.

1 **TABLES**

2

3 **Table 1.** Two pH measurements including correction of dye perturbation effects using CO₂ certified reference
 4 material from Batch 143. pH (total scale; pH_T) is reported at the temperature in the flow cell during sample
 5 analysis (T_{ref}, °C), and also normalized to 25 °C using CO2SYS and certified total alkalinity (AT; μmol kg⁻¹).
 6 The results of the overdetermination are shown in the calculated total DIC (CT; μmol kg⁻¹) and AT columns. CT
 7 values were calculated using CRM AT, salinity, phosphate, silicic acid, T_{ref}, and pH_T. AT values were calculated
 8 using CRM CT, salinity, phosphate, silicic acid, T_{ref}, and pH_T. 1 standard deviation of the calculated CT and AT
 9 values is 0.21 and 0.28 μmol kg⁻¹, respectively.

10

B143	pH _T	T _{ref}	pH _{T25}	certified		calculated	
				CT	AT	CT	AT
#1	7.9421	23.84	7.9249	2017.75	2241.04	2017.50	2241.40
#2	7.9310	24.55	7.9244	2017.75	2241.04	2017.80	2241.00

11